

1 Flight posture of birds' hindlimbs during flight: phylogeny and ecology

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3 4 Abstract

5 Birds are renowned for their ability to fly. Among other adaptations, flight requires an
6 aerodynamic profile, which birds achieve through their body shape and plumage. The posture of
7 the legs during flight, must be as unobtrusive as possible. Birds adopt two types of posture:
8 flexed or extended ankles. The posture of the hindlimbs during flight has been little investigated,
9 even though it can potentially have a significant impact on aerodynamics, prey capture, perching,
10 and more. This study investigates the factors determining hindlimb posture during flight. Using a
11 representative sample covering avian phylogeny, we test whether the distribution of postures
12 within it is random or constrained by phylogeny. We test whether posture has an impact on bird
13 morphology using their mass and tarsus length. Finally, we investigate whether posture is
14 correlated ecology, in particular perching and arboreal environments. Our results indicate that
15 posture is highly constrained by phylogeny, followed by ecology. Birds that primarily perch and
16 live in arboreal environments mostly adopt a flexed posture. We also find that birds adopting a
17 flexed posture tend to be smaller than birds with an extended posture. We propose that the
18 ancestral was the extended ankle posture, and that during the colonisation of arboreal
19 environments, the flexed posture provides a sufficiently strong adaptive advantage for it to be
20 subsequently retained. This result opens up new research perspectives in understanding flight
21 and its development in birds.

22
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Introduction

Birds are one of the tetrapod lineages that have conquered the aerial environment. This conquest has resulted in evolutionary success, with more than 10 000 recorded species, and an impressive diversity of flight types (Bruderer et al., 2010), body sizes (Chai & Dudley, 1999; Williams et al., 2020) altitudes (Laybourne, 1974) and flight distances covered (Egevang et al., 2010). Despite this diversification, flight imposes significant constraints on the bird's body, necessitating adaptations such as wing asymmetry for lift generation (Greenewalt, 1975; Rader & Hedrick, 2023), pneumatisation of the bones to lighten the skeleton (Burton et al., 2023) and a forward-shifted center of mass for improved flight maneuverability (Harvey et al., 2022). It also requires an aerodynamic profile, achieved through their body shape and plumage. The feet must not stick out, otherwise they will disrupt the airflow around the body.

However, few studies have investigated hindlimb posture during flight from an aerodynamic, ecological or biomechanical perspective. Early studies (Allen, 1903; Townsend, 1909), based on observational notes, identified two hindlimb postures during flight (Allen, 1903; Townsend, 1909). Both postures involve flexed hips and knees (Allen, 1903; McFarland & Meyers, 2008; Townsend, 1909; Walker & Meyers, 2019). The difference resides in the flexion or extension of the ankle. When the ankle is flexed, the foot forward; this posture is observed in Passeriformes, Strisores and part of Coraciiformes (Townsend, 1909). Conversely, when the ankle is extended, the foot backwards; this 'extended' posture is observed in Accipitriformes, Gruiformes and Psittaciformes (Townsend, 1909). Except during take-off and landing, or when hunting, which impose specific biomechanical constraints, to date, no bird has been identified as adopting both postures, or as possessing any other posture.

A century later, studies have examined the maintenance of knee flexion during flight (McFarland & Meyers, 2008; Walker & Meyers, 2019). The authors suggest that the muscles involved are predominantly composed of slow fibers to reduce the energetic cost of posture maintenance. However, they admit that the results are contradictory and propose that body size and posture biomechanics may explain the results obtained. McFarland & Meyers (2008) mention in their discussion that the distribution of postures in the phylogeny is relatively homogeneous, with monophyletic groups exhibiting a single posture. It is therefore likely that hindlimb posture has a phylogenetic component. They also suggested a possible correlation between morphometric traits, such as tarsus length or body mass, and posture, potentially for aerodynamic purposes. We hypothesize that ecological traits, particularly whether the habitat is more or less open, could also influence the posture of the hindlimbs during flight. This article explores the factors determining hindlimb posture during flight. We tested the following hypotheses:

1. Phylogenetic features: The posture of the hindlimbs is constrained by phylogeny.
2. Impact of mass and tarsus length: a large tarsus or body mass corresponds to an extended posture.
3. Environmental influences: the posture of the hindlimbs is affected by habitat density and an arboreal environment, as well as a primarily perching lifestyle.

Material and Methods

Creation of the database

We selected 231 bird species in 229 genera, distributed across the phylogeny and representing diverse ecologies, to achieve phylogenetic and ecological representativeness of the avian lineage. Our dataset represents $\approx 10\%$ of genera and $\approx 80\%$ of families. To assess our sampling quality, we used Faith's index, which quantifies the amount of phylogeny in a sample (Faith, 1992). To do so, we measured the amount of phylogenetic history in the entire avian lineage and in our sample (Title et al., 2022). We calculated the percentage of the total phylogenetic history contained within the bird phylogeny, we generated 10 000 random samples of the same size as our sample. This method allowed us to determine the proportion of

103 phylogenetic history in our sample relative to 10 000 random samples of the same size in the
 104 avian lineage thereby estimating the quality of our sampling strategy. To do this, we used the
 105 “faithPD” function in the “epm” package (Title et al., 2022). The Faith index is calculated by
 106 summing the lengths of all the branches of the phylogenetic tree that connect the species
 107 present in the sample (see Figure 1).

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Figure 1 - Explanation of Faith index

111 We constructed the flight posture database using the Macaulay Library
 112 (<https://macaulaylibrary.org/>) and various photographs referenced on the web. A bird was
 113 classified as having an "extended" posture if the dorsal side of the tarsus and/or the foot was
 114 visible in a ventral view. If the plantar side of the tarsus and/or the foot was visible, then the
 115 posture was considered “flexed”, see Figure 2. In rare cases where feathers interfered with
 116 identification, we relied on foot position and previous studies. All postures were identified in
 117 double-blind conditions independently by the authors. Posture identification is referenced in
 118 Supplementary Table 1. We used the AVONET database (Tobias et al., 2022) to extract other
 119 parameters. Morphometric parameters included body mass (as a size proxy) and tarsus length
 120 (length of the tarsus from the posterior notch between tibia and tarsus, to the end of the last
 121 scale of acrotarsium). Lifestyle traits included: (1) perching behavior (non-perching vs perching
 122 species, which spend most of their time above ground on branches, vegetation, rocks, buildings,
 123 posts, or wires); (2) habitat (non-arboreal vs arboreal, including woodlands and forests); and (3)
 124 habitat density (open, semi-open, or closed). All parameters are grouped in Supplementary Table
 125 2.

126

127 **Figure 2** - Identification of flying postures, (A, B, E) flexed posture, (C, D, F)
 128 extended posture, A *Pavo muticus* (ML205934031), B *Bombycilla garrulus*
 129 (ML615358904), C *Gavia stellata* (ML621419081), D *Harpia harpyja*
 130 (ML241489321), E *Tauraco corythaix* (ML166122911), F *Rynchops niger*
 131 (ML641391322). All the photographs come from Macaulay Library
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D-test

133 To determine whether posture is a phylogenetic trait, we performed the D-test (Fritz &
 134 Purvis, 2010) on the phylogeny in our sample, with 1,000,000 iterations. The D-test gives the
 135 probability that a binary trait can be randomly or non-randomly distributed in the phylogeny. The
 136 D value can be interpreted as follows: a value of 0 indicates a Brownian motion distribution, while
 137 a value of 1 indicates a random distribution. The lower the value is below 0, the more the trait is
 138 constrained by phylogeny. The higher the value is above 1, the more dispersed the trait is in the
 139 phylogeny. The method is illustrated in Figure 3. We used the “phylo.d” function in the R “caper”
 140 (Orme, 2013) package. In this way, we can test our first hypothesis: “Hindlimbs posture is
 141 constrained by phylogeny”.

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143 **Figure 3** - Explanation of D-test, each color is a character state modified from
 144 (Fritz & Purvis, 2010)
 145

Morphometric relationships

146 We conducted Wilcoxon and PhyloANOVA tests (Garland et al., 1993) using the
 147 “aov.phylo” function in the “geiger” package (Pennell et al., 2014) to determine whether there is
 148 a relationship between posture and our morphological parameters: log tarsus length, log cubic
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150 root of mass, and the ratio between log tarsus length and log cubic root of mass, each
151 PhyloANOVA was performed 100,000 times. In this way, we can test our second hypothesis, “A
152 large tarsus or body mass corresponds to an extended posture.”

153 **Ecological relationships**

154 To determine whether ecological indicators correlate with hindlimb posture, we performed
155 chi-square tests on three parameters: habitat density (closed, semi-open, open), arboreality
156 (arboreal vs. non-arboreal), and perching behavior (perching vs. non-perching). Habitat density
157 likely represents the ecological factor most closely linked to hindlimb posture, as it impacts aerial
158 locomotion. Arboreal habitat use and perching behavior provide information on leg usage
159 frequency. To define the arboreal environment, we merged the categories ‘woodland’ and ‘forest’.
160 All data comes from the AVONET database. We can thus test our third hypothesis: ‘The posture
161 of the hindlimbs is constrained by various ecological characteristics such as habitat density,
162 arboreal environment and a perching lifestyle.’ We conducted pairwise phylogenetic comparisons
163 between hindlimb posture and arboreality, and between posture and perching behavior, to
164 determine whether these ecological traits depend on posture within avian phylogeny. To do this,
165 we used the ‘fitPagel’ function from the ‘phytools’ package with “ARD” model (Revell, 2012).

166 **Phylogenetic setup**

167 We used the time-calibrated supertree proposed by (McTavish et al., 2025), from which
168 we removed species not present in our sample using the ‘drop.tip’ command from the ‘ape’
169 package. The tree published by (McTavish et al., 2025) is a tree that aims to unify the
170 phylogenies available in the literature.

171 Given the proportion of our sample comprising Passeriformes, and due to their
172 homogeneity, all statistical analyses were conducted both with and without them to ensure that
173 there are no false positives in the analyses that take phylogeny into account.

174 The full code is available in supplementary material.

175 **Results**

176 **Database representativeness**

177 The Faith index value for our phylogeny indicates that our sample contains approximately
178 9.73% of the phylogenetic history contained in the entire current avian lineage. Random draws
179 obtained an average of 7% +/- 0.7% of the phylogenetic history (Figure 4). Our sample is
180 significantly more representative of the phylogenetic diversity than a random sample would be.

181

182 **Figure 4** - Comparison between the Faith index of the sample (red dot) and the random sample

183 **TestD**

184 The results of test D indicate that the distribution of postures within the tested phylogeny is not random, but follows a clustered distribution. The value
185 of D with Passeriformes is -1.56 with p-value <0.001 and without Passeriformes is -1.25 with p-value <0.001, which corroborates the observation on the
186 visual representation (Figure 5) of the phylogeny, where we distinguish well-defined groups between the 'flexed' posture and the 'extended' posture.

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Figure 5 - Distribution of postures and ecological characteristics within the phylogeny. All the silhouettes are from PhyloPic.

189 **Morphology**

190 All results from the Wilcoxon and phyloANOVA tests are compiled in Figure 6. The
191 logarithm of the cubic root of the mass is related to posture (Wilcoxon p-value <0.001;
192 PhyloANOVA p-value = 0.002). The logarithm of tarsus length appears to be related to posture
193 (Wilcoxon p-value <0.001; PhyloANOVA p-value = 0.038). The ratio between mass and tarsus
194 has a significant relationship with posture (Wilcoxon p-value <0.001; PhyloANOVA p-value =
195 0.027). Graphically, we observed overlaps the distributions in Figure 6, indicating the absence of
196 a clear demarcation. Generally, the larger the species, the more likely it is to adopt an extended
197 posture.

198 Without Passeriformes, the posture has a significant relationship with the logarithm of the
199 cubic root of the mass (Wilcoxon p-value <0.001;PhyloANOVA p-value = 0.007) and the
200 logarithm of tarsus length (Wilcoxon p-value <0.001;PhyloANOVA p-value = 0.002). The ratio
201 between mass and tarsus has no significant relationship with posture (Wilcoxon p-value <0.128;
202 PhyloANOVA p-value = 0.211).

203

204 **Figure 6** - Distribution of morphological parameters according to posture, red:
205 extend, blue: flexed

206 **Ecology**

207 All results are summarised in Figure 7.

208 With regard to habitat density, our results indicate that the distribution of postures differs
209 significantly between closed, semi-open and open environments, with the exception of the
210 comparison between closed and semi-open environments when Passeriformes are excluded
211 from the dataset. In general, it is observed that the more enclosed the environment, the higher
212 the proportion of 'flexed' postures.

213 Our results on the perching habits of birds show that there are significantly more birds with a
214 'flexed' posture among perching species than with those without. However, the result of the
215 pairwise phylogenetic comparison is not significant (with Passeriformes p-value= 0.38; without
216 Passeriformes p-value= 0.08).

217 Our results on whether birds live in an arboreal environment show that there is a
 218 significant difference in the proportion of postures between birds living in a arboreal environment
 219 and those that do not. There are more birds with a 'flexed' posture in the arboreal environment.
 220 The pairwise phylogenetic comparison is significant (with Passeriformes p-value< 0.001; without
 221 Passeriformes p-value< 0.001).

222
 223 **Figure 7** - Distribution of the posture on ecological parameters, red: extend, blue:
 224 flexed

Discussion

225 Overview of the results

226 Our sample contains 9.73% of the total phylogenetic history of birds spread across 80%
 227 of families. This sample provides an overall representation of phylogeny, allowing us to make
 228 viable interpretations about the entire phylogeny of birds. This sample contains 43.29% of
 229 extended postures and 57.1% of flexed postures. In terms of environment, 28.57% are in a
 230 closed environment, 30.3% are in a semi-open environment and 41.13% are in open
 231 environments. As for the other indicators, 45.9% are arboreal and 48% are perching. This gives
 232 us a good representation of the ecological factors we are seeking to interpret.
 233 All of our hypotheses were tested and supported. The result of the D test and Figure 5 confirm
 234 that the distribution of postures within the phylogeny is not random and is highly constrained by
 235 phylogeny. This is visually confirmed by our tree, which shows six groups and three isolated
 236 species converging on a 'flexed' posture, as well as two reversals.

- 237 • The most notable clade is the Passeriformes, which accounts for almost 50% of our
- 238 sample.
- 239 • The Piciformes are composed of birds living mainly in closed to semi-open
- 240 environments.
- 241

242 • The Strisores with two potential cases of evolutionary reversal (*Caprimulgus affinis*,
243 *Steatornis caripensis*), one of which corresponds to open environments.
244 • The Bucerotiformes consist of one species living in open environments and one in
245 semi-open environments.

246 • The Galliformes group consists mainly of birds living in closed or semi-open
247 environments, with one species living in open environments. We observe what could be
248 described as either convergence or reversion in our phylogeny. The majority of birds living in
249 closed or semi-open environments have a 'flexed' posture.
250 • The Musophagidae consist of birds that live mainly in closed or semi-open
251 environments.

252 • Species that independently acquired the 'flexed' posture are: *Fregata magnificens* /
253 *Trogon elegans* (closed environments) / *Merops apiaster* (open environments)
254 Posture is linked to morphological indicators of size. Our results show that birds with
255 lower body mass and/or smaller tarsus size tend to have a significantly 'flexed' posture, and that
256 this trend is not explained primarily by phylogeny. With regard to the ratio of tarsus length to
257 mass, the result becomes non-significant when we incorporate phylogeny without Passeriformes.
258 We therefore find that birds with a relatively long tarsus in relation to their mass tend to have a
259 'flexed' posture, but that this tendency is entirely explained by phylogeny, as Passeriformes have
260 a proportionally longer tarsus than other birds.

261 Our results on the ecological nature of postures have identified significant differences.
262 The more closed the environment tends to be, the greater the proportion of birds with a 'flexed'
263 posture. The same is true for the arboreal environment and a mainly perching lifestyle, both of
264 which have a higher proportion of 'flexed' postures. However, based on the results of pairwise
265 phylogenetic comparisons, only the correlation between posture and arboreal habitat remains
266 significantly valid regardless of phylogeny.

267 **Interpretation**

268 We suggest that the 'flexed' posture is a consequence of the conquest of the arboreal
269 environment. The "flexed" posture is most likely an adaptive advantage in arboreal environments
270 with perching behaviours. This seems to be confirmed in Figure 5 with an overlay of the 'flexed'
271 posture with the associated ecological characteristics. The fact that the feet are positioned
272 forward, due to the 'flexed' posture, should allow for more frequent and faster landing, which
273 corresponds to behaviour in arboreal environments. However, we note a few exceptions among
274 birds with a mainly aerial lifestyle, such as *Fregata magnificens* or *Hirundo rustica*, which have a
275 flexed posture. In the first case, this could be explained by the fact that the hind legs are not used
276 most of the time or for better aerodynamics. In the second case, it seems that this can be
277 explained by phylogeny, which preserves the 'flexed' posture. This is particularly noticeable in
278 Passeriformes, which shows no reversion, even though many of them live in open environments
279 or are not primarily perching birds. In the case of Passeriformes, it would seem that the 'flexed'
280 posture does not confer any disadvantage outside of closed environments.

281 The fact that birds with a 'flexed' posture tend to be smaller than their 'extended'
282 counterparts can be explained mainly by the closed environment in which it is more difficult to
283 evolve with a large size, rather than directly by the posture itself. Regarding the proportion of the
284 tarsus relative to mass, this is not correlated with posture. The results indicating a correlation can
285 be explained by the high proportion of Passeriformes in the dataset. As Passeriformes all have a
286 'flexed' posture and a greater proportion of the tarsus relative to mass than other birds, there is a
287 confounding effect related to phylogeny. Indeed, Passeriformes differ from other birds with a
288 'flexed' posture in having a proportionally longer tarsus, which complements this previous study
289 (Xu et al., 2023). This seems to indicate that the 'flexed' posture in Passeriformes differs from
290 that of other flexed birds in anatomical aspects.

291 The 'extended' posture appears to be the ancestral state in our sample. We propose that
292 the first posture during the development of flight within the avian lineage was "extended" and that
293 the 'flexed' posture appeared convergently in different avian lineages that adopted an arboreal
294 lifestyle.

295 In terms of future research, we suggest that there may be morphological indicators on the
296 pelvic skeleton of birds, particularly passerines, that indicate the posture of the legs during flight.
297 This suggestion is based on the absence of specialised postural muscles for maintaining the legs
298 during flight (McFarland & Meyers, 2008; Walker & Meyers, 2019) and on the low or non-existent
299 muscle activity of the pelvic muscles during cruise flight (Gatesy & Dial, 1993). It would also be
300 interesting to develop aerodynamic and mechanical studies to determine whether the posture of
301 the legs during flight has an impact on flight.

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310 **Supplementary information**

311 Data, script, and supplementary information are available online:

312 **References**

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